

Application of 4'-N-p-Nitrophenyl-4-chloroazobenzene-3-sulphonic Acid as an Adsorption Indicator in Argentometry

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MEHROTRA *et al*¹ have used a number of adsorption indicators in argentometry. The use of 4'-N-p-nitrophenyl-4-chloroazobenzene-3-sulphonic acid as an adsorption indicator in argentometry is described in the present communication.

Experimental

All chemicals used were either of A.R., B.D.H. or G.R., E. Merck grade unless stated otherwise. The stock solutions of alkali halides or pseudohalides were prepared in double distilled water and standardised by the usual procedures². A 0.2% solution of the dye SGF was used as an indicator. The detailed experimental procedure has been described earlier².

Results and Discussion

4'-N-p-Nitrophenyl-4-chloroazobenzene-3-sulphonic acid (SGF dye) exhibits a sharp colour change from yellow to pink in the pH range 6-8. In this pH range, halides or pseudohalides can be titrated with silver ions giving a sharp colour change (which is also reversible) at the equivalence point due to surface adsorption³. The pink colour of the suspension or precipitate of AgX (where X = Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, SCN⁻ or N₃⁻ ion) remains persistent for some time but changes gradually on standing.

The sharpness of colour change during titration decreases in the order N₃⁻ > SCN⁻ > Cl⁻ > Br⁻ > I⁻ depending on the concentration. The titration could be satisfactorily performed in the solution with the concentration 0.002 M in case of pseudohalide and 0.005 M in case of halide ions. At the equivalence point the suspension or precipitate of AgX acquired a slight pink colour. The coagulation of AgX and the colour change occurred simultaneously and instantaneously at the equivalence point and the colour change was reversible. Therefore, the reverse titrations could also be carried out. The results are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

The colour change observed at the equivalence point is attributed to the adsorption of the dye by AgX, during which AgX-dye complex is formed and the colour of the complex is found to be identical with the colour observed at the end point. In order to substantiate this, Ag-dye complex was prepared by reacting 0.5 g of the dye with 5 ml 20% AgNO₃ solution made acidic by adding a few drops of HNO₃. The orange-red Ag-derivative of the dye was filtered, washed and dried in a desiccator. The

Ag-dye complex is fairly stable in the absence of sunlight and is sparingly soluble in water.

TABLE 1—'SGF' AS ADSORPTION INDICATOR IN ARGENTOMETRIC TITRATIONS OF HALIDE/PSEUDOHALIDE IONS

Vol. of halide/pseudohalide titrated = 10.00 ml		
Conc. of halides/pseudohalides	Vol. and Conc. of AgNO ₃	Detailed conditions
0.1 M KCl	10.00-10.05 ml of 0.1 M AgNO ₃	Coagulation occurs just at the end point. Colour changes are sharp and reversible.
0.1 M KBr/KSCN	10.00 ml of 0.1 M AgNO ₃	
0.1 M KI/NaN ₃	9.95-10.00 ml of 0.1 M AgNO ₃	
0.02 M KCl/KBr/KSCN	9.95-10.00 ml of 0.02 M AgNO ₃	Colour change occurs in susp. phase, sharp and reversible.
0.02 M KI/NaN ₃	10.00 ml of 0.02 M AgNO ₃	
0.01 M KI/KSCN	10.00-10.05 ml of 0.01 M AgNO ₃	Coagulation occurs just before, the end point.
0.01 M KCl/KBr/NaN ₃	9.95-10.00 ml of 0.01 M AgNO ₃	
0.002 M KCl/KSCN/NaN ₃	10.00 ml of 0.002 M AgNO ₃	Colour change in susp. phase, sharp and reversible.
0.002 M KBr/KI	10.00-10.05 ml of 0.002 M AgNO ₃	

TABLE 2—'SGF' AS ADSORPTION INDICATOR IN ARGENTOMETRIC TITRATION OF Ag⁺ IONS

Vol. of AgNO ₃ titrated = 10.00 ml		
Conc. of AgNO ₃	Vol. and conc. of halide/pseudohalide	Detailed conditions
0.1 M	10.00-10.05 ml of 0.1 M KCl/KSCN/NaN ₃	Coagulation occurs much earlier and dye adsorbed on coagulated ppt. but at equivalence point desorption of the dye begins.
0.1 M	9.95-10.00 ml of 0.1 M KBr/KI	
0.02 M	10.00 ml of 0.02 M of KCl/KBr/KSCN	—do—
0.02 M	10.00-10.05 ml of 0.02 M KI/NaN ₃	—do—
0.01 M	10.00-10.05 ml of 0.01 M KCl/KSCN/NaN ₃	—do—
0.01 M	10.00 ml of 0.01 M KBr/KI	

4'-N-p-Nitrophenyl-4-chloroazobenzene-3-sulphonic acid (SGF dye), is yellow in aqueous solution but imparts a pink colour to the AgX in pH range 6-8, due to surface adsorption³ in the argentometric determination of halide and pseudohalide ions (X⁻). The colour development on the surface of AgX may be attributed to the adsorption of the dye at the surface forming Ag-dye complex having high solubility product^{2,3}, at the end point of the titration. The change observed, is accompanied by a slight drop of pH at the end point (Table 3) and is ascribed to the formation of Ag-dye complex during which the proton of the -SO₃H group of the dye is made labile.

TABLE 3—VOLUME OF HALIDE OR PSEUDOHALIDE SOLUTION TAKEN=50 ml, CONCENTRATION X=0.001 M (X=NaCl, NaN₃, KBr, KI, KSCN), CONCENTRATION Ag⁺=0.01 M

%Eqvt. of Ag added	pH changes				
	I ⁻	Br ⁻	Cl ⁻	SCN ⁻	N ₃ ⁻
0	7.30	7.32	7.34	7.70	7.38
20	7.23	7.30	7.42	7.74	7.32
40	7.13	7.26	7.44	7.69	7.28
60	7.09	7.23	7.47	7.62	7.24
80	7.05	7.20	7.35	7.53	7.20
90	6.99	7.16	7.32	7.45	7.17
95	6.92	7.11	7.32	7.40	7.16
100	6.70	6.98	7.24	7.20	7.02
105	6.68	6.96	7.17	7.15	7.01
110	6.64	6.93	7.12	7.10	7.00
120	6.58	6.91	7.09	7.07	6.98
140	6.51	6.88	6.87	7.01	6.95
160	6.44	6.86	6.82	6.96	6.91

The argentometric titration of the halide/pseudo-halide (X⁻) (where X⁻=Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, N₃⁻ or SCN⁻)

using the above dye can be satisfactorily carried out within the accuracy ± 0.5 to 1%.

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